

Review Article

AI applications in healthcare and medicine: A brief Strategy and applications

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Article Info

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Received:-17-4-2024

Accepted:-22-5-2024

Published:-27-5-2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11353521

Abstract:

Advancements in AI technology are transforming healthcare and education. This article analyzes the influence of AI in different industries and discusses its advantages in various fields, such as health care administrative, medicine, robotics for surgery, drug discovery, patient care. AI-powered predictive analytics can improve the accuracy, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness of disease diagnosis and laboratory testing. In this article, we survey the current status of AI in healthcare, as well as discuss its future. The focused question explores the impact of applying AI in healthcare settings and the potential outcomes of this application. This article highlighted the applications and importance of artificial intelligence in the healthcare sector. AI in healthcare includes medical diagnosis, patient monitoring, and administrative applications. We believe that AI will play important role in future healthcare goods. Precision medicine, powered by machine learning, is a critical improvement in healthcare. These artificial intelligence/machine learning algorithms have played critical roles in critical medical applications. Successful integration of AI in healthcare is expected to improve patient outcomes, efficiency, and access to individualized, high-quality care. AI has great potential, it is not meant to replace healthcare professionals.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, administrative, medicine, robotics for surgery, drug discovery, patient care

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is quickly emerging in healthcare due to its ability to harness the power of large data and obtain insight to enhance evidence-based clinical decision-making and value-based treatment. It is critical for health executives to grasp the current status of AI technologies and how they might be utilized to improve the efficiency, safety, and access to health services, hence enabling the digitalization of healthcare. AI and similar technologies are gaining popularity in business and society, and are now being used to healthcare. These technologies have the potential to alter patient care and administrative procedures for providers, payers, and pharmaceutical companies.

In this review, we will discuss the current state of AI technologies as well as their potential to alter healthcare. We will also examine concerns concerning the selection, development, and application of AI technologies to improve care quality, access, and affordability. Finally, we will provide recommendations to assist health executives create a plan for AI integration and digital healthcare transformation. New and effective solutions have been created to address complicated real-world challenges in image interpretation, speech recognition, big data analytics, and healthcare. In the following sections, we will examine the AI technologies that are now accessible and analyze their appropriate applications in healthcare. In this article, we survey the current status of AI in healthcare, as well as discuss its future. The focused question explores the impact of applying AI in healthcare settings and the potential outcomes of this application.

AI strategy

Artificial intelligence's capacity to handle and evaluate large amounts of data is highly valued in medicine and healthcare [1,2]. Robert Hryniewicz, a data scientist, believes that healthcare personnel require further support. While humans may find patterns in data, it can be a time-consuming process that robots excel

at, especially when dealing with large datasets or scenarios. When doctors are overworked and have little time, it's easy for them to overlook important indicators that might impact a diagnosis. Artificial intelligence in healthcare can identify indications that clinicians may overlook [3]. Guided by relevant clinical questions, powerful AI techniques can unlock clinically relevant information hidden in the massive amount of data, which in turn can assist clinical decision making.[4-6]. A perfect combination of increased computer processing speed, larger data collection data libraries, and a large AI talent pool has enabled rapid development of AI tools and technology, also within healthcare [7]. AI in healthcare offers tailored health information, which is a crucial benefit. AI algorithms analyze patient data, including medical histories and lifestyle characteristics, to deliver personalized suggestions for preserving good health. This information empowers individuals to make educated decisions regarding their health. Remote monitoring is an essential use of AI in healthcare. AI-powered remote monitoring devices track patients' vital signs and warn healthcare practitioners to possible concerns. This can result in early intervention, better patient outcomes, and fewer in-person visits to healthcare institutions. In addition, an AI system can help to reduce diagnostic and therapeutic errors that are inevitable in the human clinical practice[8-14]

The first group involves ML algorithms for analyzing structured data, such as imaging, genomic, and EP data. Machine learning is used in medical applications to cluster patient features and predict illness outcomes.[15] Natural language processing (NLP) extracts information from unstructured data, such as clinical notes or medical journals, to complement and improve organized medical data. NLP algorithms convert text into structured data that may be analyzed using machine learning techniques.[16]

Deep learning, also known as neural network models, uses several layers of data to predict outcomes. The invention of deep learning (DL) has had an influence on how we view AI tools today, and it is responsible for much of the contemporary enthusiasm around AI applications. DL enables the discovery of correlations that were previously impossible to portray using traditional machine learning techniques. This is mostly based on artificial neural networks, and unlike early neural networks, which had just three to five layers of connections, DL networks contain more than ten layers. This relates to the simulation of millions of artificial neurons. Deep Mind is also being looked at for applications including mobile medical assistant, diagnostics based on medical imaging, and prediction of patient deterioration. A common application of deep learning in healthcare is recognition of potentially cancerous lesions in radiology images.[17]

Rule-Based Expert Systems

In the 1980s and beyond, AI was mostly built on expert systems with 'if-then' rules. Over the last few decades, they have been widely used in healthcare for 'clinical decision support' and continue to be so today. Many EHR providers now include a set of guidelines with their systems. Data-driven and machine learning-based technologies are gradually replacing traditional methods in healthcare[18].

One of the system's drawbacks is that it can only apply the rules to a limited extent. Bringing about changes may be difficult and time-consuming. We can circumvent constraints by implementing AI-based solutions.

AI in Diagnosis and treatment applications

Machine Learning algorithms can speed up drug development in healthcare systems, reducing the time analysts spend generalizing findings. Developing drugs via clinical testing can take years and cost a lot of money [19]. IBM Watson has received media attention for its emphasis on precision medicine,

particularly cancer diagnosis and treatment. Watson integrates machine learning with natural language processing (NLP). Early excitement for this technology has waned because to the challenges of training Watson to handle specific cancer types and integrating it into care routines and systems. While rule-based EHR systems are widely used, particularly in the NHS, they are not as accurate as machine learning-based systems. Maintaining rule-based clinical decision support systems may be difficult as medical knowledge improves and they struggle to keep up with the increasing amount of data, which is usually considered as beneficial but presents several issues in medical ethics and patient/clinician interactions.

Accuracy

Machine learning (ML) is a type of AI that relies on input data to improve accuracy and address obstacles in diagnosis [20]. Machine learning may help with decision-making, workflow management, and job automation in a cost-effective manner. Deep learning uses CNN and data mining techniques to detect patterns in data. These methods are effective for detecting illness detection trends in large datasets. These methods are useful in healthcare systems for diagnosing, forecasting, and categorizing disorders [21]. Deep learning algorithms can predict pneumonia in chest radiography with 96% sensitivity and 64% specificity, compared to radiologists' 50% and 73%, respectively [22]. AI tools can improve accuracy, reduce costs, and save time compared to traditional diagnostic methods. AI is being explored for medical diagnosis and therapy, including image analysis, X-rays, CT scans, and MRIs. AI may use machine learning (ML) to discover abnormalities, fractures, cancers, and offer quantitative measures for faster and more accurate medical diagnoses.

These ML systems used data from various sources to build the AI diagnosis such as genomic data of microorganisms, gene sequencing, metagenomic sequencing results

of the original specimen, and microscopic imaging [23].

AI can detect life-threatening illnesses early and warn professionals, allowing for quick intervention. Finally, AI can maximize healthcare resources in the ED by forecasting patient demand and guiding therapeutic selection.

Treatment Design

AI creates a cloud-based medical assistant system that collects patient information, records diagnoses, assists with testing, and organizes billing information [24]. Using a public database with information from several patient and doctor instances can help physicians provide more tailored therapies and identify comparable situations with AI technology. In the future, physicians will need to use advanced AI approaches to improve care planning and patient satisfaction throughout long-term treatments.

Managing medical records and data

The healthcare business generates huge amounts of data about patients, diagnoses, and research findings on a daily basis [26]. The use of big data analytics has enabled organizations to collaborate more efficiently with patients and make better decisions. This has led to a growing reliance on big data for various purposes, including reducing waste, streamlining hospital staff timings, remote patient monitoring, and predicting epidemics [25]. Using AI to coordinate clinical experience, information, and human contact can improve patient care quality while lowering costs. AI can examine large patient groups to identify new evidence and high-quality healthcare practices [27].

Robot assisted surgery

While completely autonomous robotic surgeons are not yet a reality, researchers are interested in applying AI to assist many elements of surgery. A group at Alpen-Adria Universität Klagenfurt uses surgical recordings as teaching material to identify particular

surgeon interventions. The algorithm detects the likelihood and specific location of a dissection or cutting on a patient's tissues or organs. Recently, Google has reported that it commenced working with the pharmaceutical giant Johnson & Johnson in designing a new surgical robot system [28]. They are not the only revivals, though. With their AXSIS robot, Cambridge advisers aspire to conquer the limitations of the da Vinci, such as its big size and incapability to work with extremely detailed and delicate tissues [29].

Surgeons play a crucial role in developing clinically relevant and high-quality technologies, supporting their transition from lab to clinic.

AI in genomic medicine

Combining AI with genetic analysis has significant potential for illness surveillance, prediction, and customized therapy [30]. Since the completion of the Human Genome Project, genomic medicine has grown rapidly as an interdisciplinary medical specialty including the use of genetic information. The fundamental concepts of genomic medicine include DNA, RNA, genome, exome, exon, codon, biomarker, germline, intron, microarray, and somatic. Genes, or tiny units of heredity, are considered to number between 20,000 and 25,000 in humans [31]. Humans inherit two copies of the gene: one from each father. The human genome comprises of coding genes (both protein and non-protein). Genes can include as little as a hundred or as many as two million DNA nucleotides [31]. As a result, the genome represents both the number of genes and the complexity of their networks [188]. "The human genome is fiercely innovative, dynamic, sections of it are unexpectedly beautiful, encrusted with history, inscrutable, vulnerable, resilient, adaptable, repetitious, and unique," Mukherjee [32] says. From DNA sequencing to phenotyping and variation detection to downstream interpretation, machine learning and deep learning have had an impact on practically every genomics investigation. Machine-

learning techniques have been used in bioinformatics activities such as genome annotation and variation effect prediction for a long time. Such advancements, together with an increase in open-access research and instrumentation, drive AI application in a variety of genomics analysis. Machine-learning approaches are being included into proprietary software vendors' genomics analysis tools and services, as well as open-source resources. In genomics, the vast majority of AI efforts are still in the research stage. Transcriptomic profiling is used in oncology to categorize tumors into therapeutically relevant categories. Molecular classifications, initially defined for breast cancer and later expanded to include colorectal, ovarian, and sarcomas, have significant consequences for diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment options [33,34]. Analyzing genetic data with clinical factors, including effectiveness and adverse effects, might help identify new therapeutic targets or repurpose current medications for new purposes [35-39]. Non-clinical toxicity is a common challenge in drug development, accounting for a considerable percentage of failures during clinical trials. Computational modeling is making it possible to forecast medication toxicity, potentially boosting therapeutic development [39].

Several companies specialize in providing genetically-based cancer diagnosis and therapy suggestions. Understanding the genetic basis of cancer and its response to new medications and regimens has become challenging for physicians. Firms like Foundation Medicine and Flatiron Health, both now owned by Roche, specialise in this approach.

Drug discovery through AI/ML

ML is being utilized on these genomic datasets for a number of purposes, including illness subtype definition, disease biomarker discovery [40] and repurposing [41], and pharmaceutical response prediction [42]. AstraZeneca and Benevolent, for example, are using AI to speed up the discovery of new

potential drug targets by combining genomes, chemistry, and clinical data. The drugmaker has also developed collaborations with AI drug discovery businesses.

Genome editing methods are increasingly being used for therapeutic objectives, such as replacing or modifying a defective gene in patients. The work improves our understanding of genes and DNA sequences. CRISPR is the most adaptable, cost-effective, and simple genome editing tool currently accessible. It is taught with ML and DL algorithms to increase its efficiency and accuracy. Pharmaceutical companies are pursuing CRISPR technology. GSK has announced a multi-million-dollar collaboration with the University of California to construct a CRISPR laboratory, with GSK's artificial intelligence division providing data analysis support.

Patient care and consultation through AI

These innovative technologies enable remote video discussions between patients and physicians, making them stand out. Typically, patients schedule appointments for certain times, typically on the same day. This gives them enough time to present detailed information for the physician to study and assess before speaking with the patient. Patients no longer need to travel to the hospital for exams. People may check their health using a variety of wearable and fitness devices. These gadgets include various health monitoring apps. Gadgets may monitor and analyze health data, providing users with insights on their current status.

Healthcare bots, such as Babylon and uMotif, can provide real-time assistance to patients via mobile messaging applications [43]. Health conversation bots can answer health-related queries and help patients manage prescriptions by offering info on various medications and recommended dosages [44]. AI-powered phone apps can provide medical services such as triaging patients and determining the urgency of their symptoms. The NHS tested an AI chatbot in north London, and around 1.2

million people now use it instead of contacting the non-emergency hotline [45].

Healthcare professionals may use AI algorithms to adjust prescription doses for specific patients and forecast probable adverse drug events, lowering risks and enhancing patient care. A study intended to create an AI-based prediction model for prothrombin time international normalized ratio (PT/INR) and a decision support system for warfarin maintenance dosage optimization [46].

AI in Administrative applications

It has several uses in healthcare, including claims processing, clinical documentation, revenue cycle management, and medical records management.

Healthcare professionals spend a significant amount of time doing paperwork, they must do time-consuming administrative responsibilities. It is inappropriate to place a medical professional responsible for patient care in such situations. This can lead to exhaustion and difficulty paying attention to patients. Agah [47] emphasizes the need of analyzing records and extracting data. To create a more employee-friendly medical workplace, technology should be employed to handle large amounts of paperwork.

The Future of AI in Healthcare

This article highlighted the applications and importance of artificial intelligence in the healthcare sector. AI in healthcare includes medical diagnosis, patient monitoring, and administrative applications. We believe that AI will play important role in future healthcare goods. Precision medicine, powered by machine learning, is a critical improvement in healthcare. These artificial intelligence/machine learning algorithms have played critical roles in critical medical applications. AI technologies are expected to supplement, not replace, human doctors in providing patient care. The advantages provided by AI models for analyzing ample, complicated biomedical information have massive potential for speeding up genetic

medicine breakthroughs. The future biotechnology will bring promising development through ML in the field of medicine [48]. AI algorithms can analyze patient data and detect subtle patterns and indicators of diseases at early stages. This can facilitate early intervention and preventive measures, potentially improving prognosis and reducing healthcare costs. Successful integration of AI in healthcare is expected to improve patient outcomes, efficiency, and access to individualized, high-quality care. AI has great potential, it is not meant to replace healthcare professionals. Instead, AI technologies should be seen as tools to augment healthcare delivery, enhance decision-making, and improve patient outcomes. Collaboration between AI experts, healthcare providers, and policymakers will be essential to address challenges, establish regulations, and harness the full potential of AI in healthcare.

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has the potential to play a significant role in enhancing the quality of medical care and helping doctors to reflect and learn from their mistakes. The quantity and breadth of applications for AI in genomics, on the other hand, are fast growing. Using AI in virtual health and mental health assistance can enhance patient treatment. To enable equitable and successful AI adoption, limitations like prejudice and lack of customization must be addressed. AI-powered predictive analytics can improve the accuracy, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness of disease diagnosis and laboratory testing. There are several ways in which AI can be utilized for this purpose. One of the key ways that AI can help is by detecting and preventing errors in medical care.

Acknowledgements: None

Conflicts of interest: All authors declared no personal or financial conflicts of interest.

Funding information

The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Informed consent: N/A.

Research involvement of Human or animals: N/A.

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